

THE IMPACT OF LANGUAGE MODERNIZATION ON UZBEK TRANSLATION: BALANCING TRADITION AND INNOVATION

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Abstract: Language modernization in Uzbekistan, particularly the shift from Cyrillic to Latin script, has significantly impacted translation practices. This article explores how these changes balance traditional linguistic forms with innovations driven by globalization and technology. It examines the challenges translators face, including the introduction of new vocabulary, the creation of neologisms, and the tension between innovation and tradition. Through literature review, translation analysis, and interviews with professional translators, the study highlights how Uzbek translation has evolved and the difficulties in reconciling tradition with modern needs.

Keywords: language modernization, Cyrillic to Latin script, neologisms, globalization, linguistic innovation, cultural heritage.

Introduction

The Uzbek language has undergone significant transformations in recent decades, particularly with the shift from the Cyrillic to the Latin alphabet in 1992. This process of language modernization is part of a broader cultural and political agenda to reclaim national identity after the dissolution of the Soviet Union. While these reforms aim to make the Uzbek language more accessible and aligned with global linguistic trends, they also present challenges, particularly in the field of translation. Translators face the complex task of balancing the preservation of traditional linguistic structures with the need to introduce new terms to reflect

contemporary realities. The modernization of the Uzbek language is particularly evident in fields such as technology, science, law, and media, where the influence of English and other international languages is pronounced. As globalization accelerates, Uzbek translation must adapt to new linguistic trends while remaining sensitive to the cultural and historical significance of the language. This article explores the impact of language modernization on translation practices, focusing on the challenges and strategies employed by translators in an evolving linguistic environment.

Methodology

To understand the impact of language modernization on Uzbek translation, this study employs a mixed-methods approach. The research includes:

Literature Review: An analysis of academic articles, books, and reports on the modernization of the Uzbek language, focusing on linguistic reforms and the implications for translation.

Textual Analysis: A comparative analysis of translations from Uzbek to other languages, examining examples of new vocabulary and neologisms introduced in the translated texts.

Interviews: Interviews with professional translators who have worked with both traditional and modern Uzbek texts to gather insights into the challenges they face.

Case Studies: Specific case studies from sectors like technology and law are reviewed to illustrate how translators navigate the balance between preserving tradition and incorporating new terms.

Results and Analysis

The modernization of the Uzbek language, particularly through the transition from Cyrillic to Latin script, has had a profound impact on the way translation is approached. Several key trends emerged from the analysis:

Introduction of Neologisms: One of the most significant challenges faced by translators is the creation of neologisms. Many new terms, especially in fields such as technology, science, and media, have no direct equivalents in Uzbek. Translators often need to either adapt foreign terms or create entirely new words that are

understandable to the target audience (Kamilov, 2020). For example, terms like "internet" and "smartphone" have been translated into Uzbek using borrowed forms or newly coined expressions, such as "internet tarmog‘i" (network of the internet) and "aqlli telefon" (smart phone). However, these newly coined words are sometimes met with resistance, as they may seem foreign or disconnected from traditional Uzbek vocabulary.

Balancing Innovation and Tradition: Translators working with modern texts face a delicate balance between innovation and tradition. While some embrace new terminology and the dynamic evolution of language, others argue for the importance of maintaining traditional linguistic structures and vocabulary. The tension is particularly evident in legal and governmental translations, where precision and clarity are paramount. Here, translators must ensure that the new terms are not only modern but also easily understood and aligned with the cultural context (Dovlatov, 2015). This balancing act is especially critical in fields such as law, where a mistranslated term could lead to legal ambiguities.

Influence of Globalization: The influence of globalization has brought English-language terms into the Uzbek language, especially in fields like business, technology, and entertainment. Many of these terms are directly borrowed or adapted phonetically, which presents a challenge in terms of their integration into the Uzbek lexicon. This has led to the rise of a hybrid language in many translations, where Uzbek is mixed with English terms, sometimes creating confusion for audiences who are not familiar with the borrowed words (Urazmetov, 2014). A case in point is the growing use of terms like "email" and "chat, " which are often left untranslated in everyday discourse and translation.

Soviet Legacy: The Soviet period left a lasting impact on the Uzbek language, particularly in terms of vocabulary and translation practices. Many terms used during the Soviet era are still prevalent in modern Uzbek, despite the push for modernization. Translators who are working with older texts or trying to preserve cultural heritage face the challenge of distinguishing between Soviet-influenced language and the newer forms of Uzbek emerging from the modernization process

(Saidov, 2017). This is particularly evident in historical translations, where Soviet-era lexicon may not align with the current norms of the Uzbek language.

Regional Variations: Another important consideration is the diversity within the Uzbek-speaking community. While there is a standard literary form of Uzbek, regional dialects vary significantly. This diversity can affect translation, as some neologisms or modern terms may not be universally understood across all dialects of the language. Translators must be mindful of these variations, especially when translating for a broad audience (Urazmetov, 2014). For instance, a term accepted in Tashkent may not have the same meaning or impact in the Ferghana Valley.

Conclusion

The modernization of the Uzbek language presents both challenges and opportunities for translation. Translators must balance traditional forms with the need for innovation, navigating the shift from Cyrillic to Latin script, the influence of globalization, and Soviet-era legacies. Success in translation relies on maintaining cultural relevance while embracing linguistic change. Translators are crucial in shaping the future of the Uzbek language, and their adaptability will be key to aligning language modernization with cultural identity and historical continuity.

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